

Preoperative Optimization in Complex Ventral Hernia, Case Report in A Secondary Care Unit

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ABSTRACT

An incisional hernia is a common complication following abdominal surgery. Some hernias gradually develop into large incisional hernias or complex ventral hernias, making repair more difficult. Complex abdominal wall defects represent one of the more challenging dilemmas faced by general surgeons.

We report the case of a 42-year-old Mexican male with history of abdominal trauma secondary to a firearm which required an exploratory laparotomy a year ago, with subsequent appearance of a complex ventral hernia of 10.6 cm wide and 24.5 cm long. The patient received preoperative preparation with botulinum toxin type A and progressive pneumoperitoneum and underwent a ventral plasty with transversus abdominal release (TAR). The postoperative course was uneventful and the patient was referred for clinical surveillance. This case was successfully resolved in a secondary care unit using materials available in our hospital.

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INTRODUCTION

An incisional hernia is a common complication following abdominal surgery. Hernias can derive from a variety of sources, including a history of trauma, previous surgery, congenital defects, infection, and even cancer. Some hernias gradually develop into complex ventral hernias, making repair more difficult. Although a surgical mesh and component separation are widely used, high rates of hernia recurrence and morbidity remain considerable challenges. (1,2)

The difficulty seen in repairing these defects depends on a multitude of factors. These include the location, size, depth, and condition of the surrounding tissue associated with the defect. Hernia width over 10 cm was considered an important cut-off for complexity. (2,3)

Primary closure of fascial defects was originally the mainstay of therapy in hernia repair. Unfortunately, recurrence rates were unacceptable. Recent studies have reported that the recurrence rates of incisional hernias following open repair and laparoscopic repair are 9–12.3% and 7–10.6%, respectively. (1,2)

For this reason, surgeons are now shifting their focus away from operative technique and heightened emphasis on optimizing patient-related factors. Among the new strategies for managing complex hernias is the preoperative prehabilitation of the abdominal wall. Prehabilitation focuses on modifying patient risk factors to improve surgical outcomes. The three most commonly used adjuncts are botulinum toxin A (BTA), progressive preoperative pneumoperitoneum (PPP), and soft tissue expanders. (2,4) PPP involves using an intraperitoneal catheter to fill the intraabdominal cavity with gas, air is commonly used. The gas is thought to act as a pneumatic soft tissue expander. (4) PPP can increase the volume of the abdominal cavity, facilitate the reintroduction of the hernia contents into the abdominal cavity, and improve respiratory adaptation. (1) BTA is a neurotoxin produced by bacterium *Clostridium botulinum* that blocks acetylcholine receptors at the neuromuscular junction; it is typically injected under ultrasound guidance into the lateral abdominal wall muscles, it causes flaccid paralysis and lengthening of the lateral

Preoperative Optimization in Complex Ventral Hernia, Case Report in A Secondary Care Unit

abdominal muscles, thereby facilitating surgical closure and repair. (1,4).

Soft tissue expanders are implants placed in various position in the abdominal wall, between muscle layers, subcutaneously with the goal to mobilize soft tissue and fascia to facilitate reconstruction. The implants are typically left in situ until there is adequate soft tissue recruitment. (4) Complex hernias not only involve greater surgical difficulty, but also entail certain limitations when trying to perform abdominal prehabilitation, that is why it is important to report this case, because the prehabilitation protocol was carried out using only materials from the unit and using lower doses of

BTA than those reported in other cases, obtaining equally favorable results.

CASE PRESENTATION

A 42 year old mexican male presented with a complex hernia defect. Medical history: no chronic degenerative diseases, history of penetrating abdominal trauma by firearm requiring exploratory laparotomy with resection and anastomosis in 2025. Subsequent development of a hernia defect. Physical examination reveals a large defect where aponeurotic edges are not palpable due to the large size of the defect.

Image of the hernia defect at the first medical evaluation

No relevant alterations were found in laboratory tests

Parameter	Patient value	Reference range	Interpretation
Hemoglobin (g/dL)	14.1	12-26	Normal
Hematocrit (%)	41.3	36-46	Normal
Platelets (x10 ⁹ /L)	239	150-400	Normal
PT (seconds)	12.2	10-14	Normal
INR	1.11	0.8-1.2	Normal
aPTT (seconds)	33.6	26-35	Normal

Table 1: laboratory findings in this patient and reference ranges. PT: prothrombin time, INR international normalized ratio, aPTT: activated partial thromboplastin time.

The abdominal CT scan shows a hernia defect measuring 245.56 mm in length and 106.6 mm in width, classifying it as a complex hernia.

Preoperative Optimization in Complex Ventral Hernia, Case Report in A Secondary Care Unit

Abdominal CT scan images showing the craniocaudal axis of the abdominal cavity, the anteroposterior axis from the anterior surface of the vertebral body to the inner surface of the anterior abdominal wall, and the hernial sac in its three maximum axes.

Abdominal wall defect with remaining aponeurotic margins.

Prehabilitation of the abdominal wall begins four weeks prior to surgery with the application of 100 IU of botulinum toxin type A. 50 IU are applied to the left and right flanks, distributed at five different points using the midclavicular line, anterior axillary line, and mid-axillary line as reference points.

After four weeks, the patient is admitted and a central venous catheter is placed at the Palmer point to initiate progressive pneumoperitoneum. 500 cc of air is administered twice daily for five days. The patient does not report any incidents or symptoms during these days

Preoperative Optimization in Complex Ventral Hernia, Case Report in A Secondary Care Unit

At the end of the five days of progressive pneumoperitoneum, the patient undergoes an open ventral abdominis repair. A transversus abdominis release is performed. The hernial contents are reduced, and the posterior fascia is closed with a continuous suture of non-absorbable material. A polypropylene mesh is placed in a retromuscular position and fixed with interrupted sutures to the aponeurotic edge.

Subsequently, the anterior fascia was closed with a continuous suture of non-absorbable material, achieving tension-free approximation of the linea alba. The skin was then closed with staples. Intraoperative findings included a 14x25 cm ventral hernia and firm adhesions to the abdominal wall.

Preoperative Optimization in Complex Ventral Hernia, Case Report in A Secondary Care Unit

The patient remained under observation with a normal diet and was discharged without incident in the three days following surgery. At the outpatient follow-up, the staples were removed 10 days post-surgery. The patient was reported to be asymptomatic.

DISCUSSION

Complex ventral hernias currently represent one of the greatest challenges in abdominal wall surgery due to their association with loss of domain, biomechanical alterations, multiple reinterventions and a high rate of postoperative complications. These anatomical defects cause significant limitations for patients, even affecting their social and psychological well-being and reducing their ability to perform physical and social activities. The natural history of abdominal hernias has demonstrated that over time, a patient's quality of life will worsen and if left untreated, they can result in substantial complications. (2)

Recent definitions emphasize that complexity depends not only on the size of the defect but also on patient factors and the technical difficulty of the reconstruction, necessitating a comprehensive and multidisciplinary approach from the preoperative period (5).

In recent decades, the therapeutic approach has evolved from exclusively surgical repair to preoperative optimization or prehabilitation strategies aimed at improving the patient's physiological and anatomical condition before surgical reconstruction. Among these strategies, the combination of BTA and preoperative progressive pneumoperitoneum significantly increases the rates of complete fascial closure in giant hernias (6). Abdominal prehabilitation even reduces the risk of postoperative complications such as abdominal compartment syndrome (7).

In this context, prehabilitation is especially important in patients with loss of domain, obesity, sarcopenia, or giant defects, where conventional repair is associated with high morbidity and mortality. With a focus on perioperative optimization, it is hoped to improved success. (2)

One of the most relevant advances in preoperative preparation has been the use of botulinum toxin type A, which generates temporary relaxation of the lateral abdominal muscles, increasing muscle length and decreasing fascial closure

tension. The anatomical impact of botulinum toxin has been corroborated by tomographic studies, findings that objectively support its preoperative utility (8,9). In our unit, unlike other cases reported in the literature, we used only 100 IU of botulinum toxin type A due to the difficulty in obtaining it in a secondary care unit. However, despite using doses below the recommended amount, with the support of progressive pneumoperitoneum and the surgical technique employed, a satisfactory result was achieved, completely closing the hernial defect without postoperative complications. (1)

Among the other abdominal prehabilitation strategies that can be replicated in a secondary care unit is progressive pneumoperitoneum. In our case, we used a central venous catheter and air administration to perform it. The available evidence increasingly supports this strategy.(6)

Other measures that should be assessed in the preoperative period include weight loss, metabolic control of diabetes mellitus, and smoking cessation. Although these are not determining factors for a good outcome, it is suggested that they be assessed individually prior to surgery to reduce the risk of complications. In the reported case, the patient was instructed to reduce weight during the 4-week period following the application of botulinum toxin. (10) During the follow-up period, in addition to evaluating surgical results, the patient's functionality, mental health, and quality of life are assessed. In this case, the patient continues under close monitoring with scheduled monthly appointments for the next three months, as recommended by some protocols. (11)

The use of prehabilitation strategies increases the likelihood of anatomical fascial closure, reduces stress on the repair, and potentially decreases complications and recurrence. The case presented reflects the importance of adequate preoperative preparation in complex ventral hernias, not only because the results were satisfactory but also because this protocol was

Preoperative Optimization in Complex Ventral Hernia, Case Report in A Secondary Care Unit

successfully implemented using only resources available in this unit.

CONCLUSION

Complex ventral hernias present a challenging surgical condition requiring a multidisciplinary and individualized approach. Preoperative rehabilitation, particularly through the use of botulinum toxin type A and progressive pneumoperitoneum, has been shown to improve the anatomical conditions for abdominal wall reconstruction.

This case demonstrates that implementing abdominal rehabilitation strategies in patients with complex ventral hernias is feasible even in resource limited settings. Proper preoperative planning and an individualized approach are key tools for improving the management of this condition in non specialized units.

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